

Association of Metallic Ions with Azide: Polarographic Study

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The association of thallium (I), cadmium, and zinc ions with azide has been studied polarographically by the method of DeFord and Hume² in aqueous solution at 25° and at a constant ionic strength (1, 2) in sodium perchlorate medium. For the sake of comparison the association of cadmium and thallium (I) ions with chloride and of thallium (I) with sulphate have been studied under comparable conditions. The various species, which appear to be present in the solutions, and their overall formation constants are given below:

TlX_3 , 2.5; $TlCl$, 1.55; $TlSO_4^-$, 2.2; CdN_3^+ , 7.8; $Cd(N_3)_2$, 23.6; $CdCl^+$, 8; ZnN_3^+ , 3 and $Zn(N_3)_2$, 15.5. The results indicate that azide has a complexing ability which is comparable to that of chloride.

Azide being a pseudo-halide like thiocyanate gives similar reactions with metal ions¹ and is expected to form complexes as well. Although the complexes of several metals with thiocyanate have been studied recently similar work with azide is lacking. By making use of the polarographic method of DeFord and Hume², the formulas and formation constants of the various species formed by thallium (I), cadmium, and zinc ions with azide ion have now been studied in aqueous solution. In order to compare the relative co-ordinating power of azide with that of other common anions, the association of thallium (I) and cadmium with chloride and of thallium (I) with sulphate have been studied under identical conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of the perchlorates of the metals were prepared by shaking a little excess of the metal carbonate (pure) with dilute perchloric acid (A. R., B. D. H.) and filtering. These were standardised by usual methods.

Sodium perchlorate (L. R., B. D. H.) and sodium azide (L. R., B. D. H.) were purified by crystallisation from water. In case of the latter, acetone was added to precipitate the pure salt from aqueous solution. Sodium chloride and sodium sulphate used were of G. R., E. Merck, quality. Stock solutions of all these were prepared and standardized as usual. The azide solution was never stored over a week.

Distilled water redistilled with alkaline permanganate from an all-glass apparatus was used for preparing the solutions. A Cambridge pH-meter (bench type) was used for measurements of pH of solutions. A Cambridge pen-recording polarograph was used for recording the polarograms.

Procedure.—The solution containing the metal perchlorate (1 mM), sodium salt of the anion (azide, chloride or sulphate as the case may be) and enough sodium perchlorate

1. Senise, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 4196.

2. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321.

for proper ionic strength (μ , 2) was adjusted to a pH of 5.5-6.0 (for this dilute perchloric acid was added to solutions containing azide), transferred to the polarographic cell dipping in a constant temperature bath maintained at $25^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. The solution was deaerated with pure nitrogen as usual and the polarogram was recorded using a dropping mercury electrode (in $2M$ $NaClO_4$ in open circuit $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.95 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$) dipping in the solution which was connected to the saturated calomel reference electrode through an agar + $NaClO_4$ - $NaCl$ soln.-agar + KCl bridge such that the resistance of the entire set-up was ca. 600 ohms. Reversibility of the wave was tested by making the usual 'log plot' from which the $E_{1/2}$ value was also obtained. The experiment was repeated with similar solutions containing different amounts of the anion. From the $E_{1/2}$ and i_d values for solutions at different concentrations of the anion, X , the various $F_n(X)$ values were calculated following DeFord and Hume².

DISCUSSION

The formation constants were all evaluated graphically as shown in Fig. 1 in which the functions $F_n(X)$ have the usual significance² and (X) stands for the concentration of

FIG. 1: (a), $Tl^+ - N_3^-$; (b), $Tl^+ - Cl^-$; (c) $Tl^+ - SO_4^{2-}$; (d), $Cd^{2+} - N_3^-$; (e), $Cd^{2+} - Cl^-$, (f) $Zn^{2+} - N_3^-$.

the anion in the solution. In order to overcome possible complications due to hydrolysis, the investigations were all carried out at a pH of 5.5-6.0, the exact pH values were record-

ed with a pH-meter. In case of the solutions containing azide, the concentration of azide needed for the evaluation of the formation constants was evaluated from the measured pH, the analytical concentration of azide in the solution, and the known dissociation constant (1.95×10^{-3} at 25°) of hydrazoic acid. For the other anions, the actual analytical concentrations were used directly. In all these cases the decrease in anion concentration in solution due to complex formation was neglected as this was too small under the experimental conditions in solutions containing excess of the anion. The formula of the highest species present in any system was given by that particular value of n for which $F_n(X)$ is a constant, independent of (X) value. The overall formation constant, β_n , of a species MX_n is given by $\lim F_n(X)$. From an analysis of the experimental data, the formulas and overall formation constants of the various species formed in the systems investigated were obtained as follows:

The results indicate that azide ion possesses a complexing ability which is comparable to that of chloride.

Recently Senise and Weves³ have reported on similar studies on the cadmium—azide system in which evidence has been given for the formation of all the species upto $\text{Cd}(\text{N}_3)_3^{-3}$ and their formation constants have been reported. These investigators, however, carried out experiments under conditions which allowed a rather large variation in pH of the solutions resulting in a possible competition of hydroxide and azide ions for the metal ion and as such their data are merely the apparent and not the true formation constants of the azide complexes. The investigations reported in this paper were carried out in the Inorganic Chemistry Department of the Indian Association for the Cultivation of Science, Calcutta, in 1960.

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